

**THE ROLE OF INFORMATION CULTURE IN PERSONALITY
FORMATION IN MODERN SOCIETY AND ITS IMPACT ON THE
NATIONAL MENTALITY**

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Annotation

In this article, the rapid development of information and communication technologies in today's information age is reducing time and distance and opening a wide path to the knowledge of world civilization. From the energy of information generated in society, we learn about the extremely urgent problems of the formation of Information Culture in society in the protection of members of society, especially young people with the future of society. The fact that human civilization is stepping into an informed society begins to pose such serious problems as timely preparation of people for new living conditions and professional activities in a highly automated information environment, training them to act independently in this environment, effectively use the capabilities of the environment and protect against negative influences. Problems in the formation of an informed society, first of all the problem of the place of man in this society, are today the subject of the focus of the international community.

Keywords: Media, Information Resource, industrial society, informatization, information war, social space, information attack, mass culture, globalization, mintalitet information security.

What is information culture and why do we need Information Culture? From this, there are views that distinguish the interpretation of this concept from the “culture” and “information” approaches. Within the framework of the culture approach, Information Culture is seen as a way of human habitation activity in an informed society, as the organizer of the process of formation of human culture.

In the framework of the information approach, however, it is viewed as a complex of knowledge of all information activities aimed at satisfying information demand. In recent times, however, the trend towards a holistic view of the concept of Information Culture in the situation of integration of information and cultural components of an individual is increasing.

And as a result of this, information culture is considered as an aspect of universal culture. It is this vision that makes it possible to reveal the true essence of Information Culture. On October 10, 2020, the decision was made' on measures to further improve the educational system in the field of Information Technology, develop scientific research and integrate them with the IT industry", the information culture is a systematized complex of knowledge, skills and skills aimed at meeting the need for information that arises in the process of Educational, Scientific - cognitive, independent. In general, it is envisaged that information culture is knowledge and skills of effective use of information and consists of various knowledge of the search for the necessary information from information resources through all manifestations of Information Technology[1]. From this definition, let's look for an answer to the question of why we need Information Culture. With the increasing value of information in society, it is evolving from an industrial society to an informed society.

The extreme variability of current life creates a number of new attributes in an informed society: Information and knowledge become the main transforming force of society; the renewal cycle of producer and social technologies takes 6-8 years from the picture of the alternation of generations, continuing education and the ability to acquire a new specialty become an integral part of maintaining an individual's social status, The possibility of forming an informational culture in students is not limited only to the independent work of students and the work of the audience.

In extracurricular activities, Information Culture Not only increases the

cognitive activity of students, but also forms the desire to study information technologies in depth, and also forms the qualifications of Information Culture for scientific purpose. Information-English” Information " - information to explain, to describe is one of the main concepts of modern science and politics, it is information that is initially transmitted by people, oral, later written or other forms[2]. Since the middle of the 20th century, it has been beginning to realize interpersonal, human-automaton, automaton-automatic information and signal exchange in animals and plants, the transmission of certain signs to the cell in a cell, and so on.

Information resources-a set of separate documents and documents in information systems, such as a particular library, archive, fund, data bank.As such, Today a Presidential Decree has been adopted on measures to approve the digital Uzbekistan 2030 strategy and its effective implementation, which means that all information resource centers and all work processes in labor activity have switched to an electronic system, according to which educational modernization is intended in particular to conduct classes using modern technologies in an interactive form. Therefore, in all business activities, a complete transfer to an electronic system without excess paper is envisaged today, this system is operating in its power. Socio-political information is a set of knowledge, information and messages that are considered the subject of exchange between members of society, social groups, political organizations in relation to social and political life and that they use in their activities.

Socio-political information is becoming increasingly important and priority in the implementation of human relations, political processes, management of society, organization of scientific, educational and educational work, promotion and propaganda. Science plays an important role in the development of socio-political information, the dissemination of which plays an important role in the development of socio-political information, the completeness, justification and

reliability. Information Culture has technical-technological and socio - cultural aspects. Technically-technologically, information culture refers to a system of knowledge about technical-information tools and methods of their rational use that serve to obtain, process, store and deliver information.

In the socio - cultural sense, Information Culture refers to the vital activity of a person in the information space, mastering certain spiritual-moral, political, legal and aesthetic values. The culture of information consumption embodies the knowledge, ability and competence in sorting information that serves social progress from the information world.

Meanwhile, the informational process also presents a number of problems: these include problems with phenomena ranging from “soft erotica”to “open pornography”. The Prevention of such situations cannot be taken completely. After all, the operation of information networks without interruptions is an important sign of its quality, and this process is experiencing constant improvement. So, no matter how impeded the path of “problems” as above, there will always be an opportunity to “bypass” them. Another problem is related to copyright as well as intellectual property rights violations. Therefore, it is natural for regions that cannot be seen by many in the information network to occur. This is also the fact that today companies spend large amounts of money to protect their information and prevent unauthorized access. At the same time, abuses can also arise that manifest themselves in manifestations ranging from the concealment of certain information and its illegal publication.

The practice of its consumption can vary dramatically in different groups, as information affects representatives of different social strata, professional and national groups in different ways. This is primarily manifested in the difference between the amount of information sources[4].

Young people show a high level of communicative activity due to their mobility and commitment to innovation and the possession of a leisure resource.

In other groups, relative passivity is observed. Such characteristics inherent in them can also cause negative consequences. This is determined by the fact that for the first group there is a risk of succumbing to the increasingly active aggressive political influence, and for the second group, it remains outside the influence of information with a positive content. Social space is also an information space at the same time. In the context of globalization, the size of information volume, their distribution through modern fast-paced tools, is ensuring that the information sphere is fundamentally different from other forms of social space. In Particular, O.I.Sokolova is an associate professor of the Department of professional communication of the Russian philologist var us. In his opinion, “the information environment of Higher Education is an area of activity that, using a set of programmatic technical , organizational methodological tools, provides educational, scientific communication with the rapid use of information, carries out the storage, processing and transmission of information” says [4].

Information consumption is a phenomenon aimed at satisfying social, or rather, spiritual needs. Information consumption is a specific form of service consumption. As you know, before consuming any service, attention is paid to its quality, price, benefits, convenience and other similar characteristics. In this process, the supply and demand characteristics of the service being consumed are also taken into account. For example, the consumption rate of services with a reduced supply is high, and the demand for them increases. These features are also inherent in the process of information consumption. However, it is worth noting that the consumption of information, which is a spiritual blessing, is also distinguished by its own aspects.

In particular, information is consumed by a concrete person, social group, Nation, society and the state-so that at these levels the processes of consumption differ from each other. For example, information that is interesting to an individual may be irrelevant to a particular social stratum or group. Information

also has spatial and temporal characteristics. Chunionchi, information that is extremely popular in the West, can be poorly consumed by the peoples of the East. In addition, information that is met with great interest in a particular historical period may become commonplace over time and not be perceived in this way in social life. Information consumption is achieved in stages that are inextricably linked with each other, such as acceptance, understanding, interpretation, regardless of who is consumed by it.

Obviously, the desire to have the necessary information is a requirement of the period. Today, however, it is also important that the individual, the social group, the nation, society and the state disseminate information about themselves. There are two main aspects to this. First of all, for example, in the current period, when the possibilities of the Internet network are expanding, it is necessary to use them extensively in strengthening the position of our country in the world community. Why, we do not have the technique and technology of this process at the level of demand. A program has not been developed to include the best examples of our national values, history and heritage, of today's science, art and literature on the Internet". The second important aspect is that the promotion and promotion of information on a global scale in response to information being disseminated from certain nonlinear, narrow-minded interests in the life of our country acts as a kind of shield against external information attacks. This is an important condition for reducing the impact of information attacks within various geopolitical interests and ensuring the security of the National Information Space. It is worth noting that the nonlinear information attack, when viewed from the point of view of today, has a significant solution to the problems associated with internet networks and its use. It is only in the matter of further increasing the role of the National mentalitetntng in the education of the younger generation that the national mentality should act as a "filter" in keeping them from the flow of various harmful information, that we are confused.

Information consumption culture also performs a number of functions, such as other forms of culture. Among them are such functions as communicative, regulatory, informational, axiological. Within the framework of the problem we are analyzing, the axiological function of the culture of information consumption is of particular importance. For example, the fact that, along with a lot of positive information through the internet, information is also transmitted that negatively affects the culture of the East, in particular, the behavior of our people, can naturally negatively affect the ideological upbringing of our people, especially young people. Only by forming a culture of information consumption can such effects be avoided. "Also "" we sometimes speak with regret that Western culture is entering without interruption. This is such a strong current that it is very difficult to challenge it. There is only one way to do this. It also consists, if any, in the timely introduction of information that is relevant to us into the internet" the whole point is in who uses this important resource and for what purposes.

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan"on the fundamentals of state policy on Youth " provides for violation of etiquette among young people, including any behavior aimed at promoting violence, embarrassment and cruelty, to be carried out in a manner of accuracy and transparency protected by blood[5]. And the law"on guarantees of the rights of the child " establishes a ban on the distribution of literature, screening films that tell about obscenity, cruelty and violence, insult human dignity, harmful effects on children and cause them to commit offenses[6].

It is necessary to achieve regular communication with young people, enrich the internet with websites that reflect our national values and traditions, introduce restrictions on the use of websites that do not comply with the rules of etiquette when connecting educational institutions to the internet, form a culture of using information resources in young people. It is necessary to ensure that the population has impartial and truthful information, to create conditions for the formation of ideological immunity in the thinking of each citizen, to strengthen

spiritual and educational propaganda against the actions of our ideological opponents, to make moral threats to our national legislation on minors, to make necessary amendments and additions aimed at preventing information attacks.

In some European states, the law defines the closure of inappropriate sites. In Russia, however, a “safe internet Center” was established to combat various information attacks. In total, the European Union has adopted 6 legislative acts in this regard, and the program “Safe internet” has been developed. In developed countries, many technologies, filtering software have also been created for parental control[7]. In particular, the Chinese government is gradually tightening its control over the internet. The country has a block on Western internet resources such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube. In 2012, registration with a real name was established in China on the popular microblogging portal Sina Weibo [8]. The Chinese government claims that control over the internet must also be established to stop people who spread accusations and pornography while appearing anonymous, as well as spreading unsubstantiated rumors and causing panic.

Currently, one of the main ways to artificially create political opposition in any country remains specially selected and intensively distributed information. The attempt to control the consciousness thinking of the world public through an information attack is becoming the main method of political struggle. In particular, the formation of pro-Western governments in different countries with the help of “color revolutions”, periodically carrying them out by means of spreading various rumors, keeping them in check, encouraging opposing forces through various international foundations under the guise of strengthening democracy and civil society, driven against each other and against the government-all this is a new political expansion technology. It looks at the ethical standards of technology, and in some cases even at the standards of international law. Thus, the information attack became not only a political struggle, but also

one of the tools of political expansion.

So, the joint development of spirituality and the economy is becoming especially relevant in the context of globalization, when the information attack has intensified. Because in such a situation, information about any social, political, economic, cultural-spiritual problem spreads very quickly among the population, causing the emergence of various tense situations. And such problems are treated by internal and external forces from the point of view of their own benefit. Some attempt to use them for mercenary purposes.

Today, even in the satisfaction of spiritual needs influenced by globalization, standardization has begun to find a decision. This process today covers rock and pop music, video and affordable films of various genres, serials, colorful entertainment shows, games. The accentuation in the mask of popular culture has appeared and is becoming more and more widespread. It is not for nothing that the first president of our country, ham, warns with great concern about this: as we build the foundations of a new life in our country, we must pay special attention to one issue. That is, one should not forget that the ideology of the old system and its ideological emptiness that arose in society after the rejection of moral norms can be used to close and enter from the outside a “mass culture”, completely alien to us, containing vices of spiritual and moral abyss.

Naturally, under the guise of “mass culture”, moral depravity and violence, the dissemination of the ideas of individualism, egocentrism, the acquisition of wealth at the expense of reason if necessary, infertility to the spiritual foundations of several thousand years of traditions and values of other peoples, lifestyle, risky taxdids aimed at ruining them do not concern a person.

The first conclusion that arises from this idea is that works that promote ideas that mentally erode the human personality, such as corruption and violence, by masking mass culture, have nothing to do with real culture. It is known that culture is divided into” elite culture “and”popular culture”. In the past, popular

culture has existed in such manifestations as epics sung by folk Bakhshis, public performances at sayings, weddings - medicine, asceticism and ridicule, folk songs. Therefore, he was distinguished by his folkishness, goodness and humanistic spirit. But today it is considered not a component of popular culture, but folklore or traditional folk culture. In the West, attempts are strong to squeeze it out of everyday life towards yetnographic museums or folk festivals held in ahyon.

What is the charm of popular culture? Why is it strong to strive for it? Studies show that even young people belonging to the same people have a similar predisposition to mass culture, despite the fact that they are from different social strata. As noted above, this condition is primarily a consequence of the convergence of the lifestyle, life views and criteria of different peoples in the conditions of urbanization and globalization, the standardization of leisure and consumption. But the reasons for the intensification of the influence of popular culture are not only those. The pursuit of mass culture is caused by long-standing passions inherent in the human race, natural-social egalitarian inclinations that have been living for centuries in its consciousness, as well as archetypes associated with the psychology of communalism. They determine to some extent the instinctive aspiration of all people to certain positive or negative things, regardless of nationality, language, religion and culture. The peculiarity of form and simplicity in content to popular culture seems to give it an egalitarian, that is, egalitarian and Democratic tone.

For example, wearing jeans and a T-shirt or a sweater and a krassovka instead of dressing in a classic style seems to be an expression of calm modesty, liberalism. In the image of such a state, supposedly fair equality-yegalitarianism is manifested. These are psychological reasons that influenced the spread of popular culture. But there are also socio – political, socio - economic, aesthetic and other reasons associated with the prevalence of popular culture. Z.Bjezinski is an

American sociologist and political scientist, who has a soul in his opinion that on the basis of the attractiveness of mass culture lies an American democracy, which attaches special importance to social egalitarianism, and at the same time does not deny individualism and individual success[9]. Even the diminution of world-famous political figures - by names in the form of yerlash-reflects, in Bjezinski's view, how far from formality American popular culture is. And the main social reason for the spread of popular culture is the crisis-turning of traditional Western values and spirituality.

A person who cannot reach full life in the real world supposedly enjoys well-being, a “beautiful marriage” in a virtual way through films and series. It is this compensatory nature of popular culture that makes it attractive to avom. While such works give a pleasant mood to an ordinary person, his most modern forms, such as computer games, are mentally subjecting a person to a monitor, or rather, to the game in it.

In the past, the role of compensator has been performed by religious pandemics, but now the mass culture is performing.

To reduce the negative consequences of globalization, as much as possible the effects of counterintelligence in the mask of mass culture and the attack of various offensive, nonlinear information, it is necessary to raise the political consciousness, legal, moral, aesthetic culture of the population, especially young people. It is of particular importance to educate the noble generation in the spirit of respect for national and universal values, masterpieces of culture from childhood, to form in them a critical attitude to certain manifestations inherent in mass culture, ideological immunity to reflection, various destructive ideas and information.

Article 1 of the law “on the media” of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that all newspapers and magazines, radio and television in our country are the main means of bringing to the world. [11] On the basis of this law, the media are

developing, the ranks are expanding. Just a few years ago, it was pointless to think about independent and electronic newspapers, cable and private televide, as well as radios. A special place is occupied by the media in the formation of public opinion, the assimilation of the national customs, rituals and traditions of our ancestors, first of all, into the minds of the younger generation. They are the process of spiritual and educational reforms, the most effective means of quickly reflecting the problems in this regard on various aspects of the life of society. Information security-a multifaceted field of activity that can bring him success only in a systematic, integrated approach.To solve this problem, legal ,administrative, procedural V software-technical measures are used.Information protection is becoming the primary issues of the state , the level of Public Policy [12].

In conclusion, it can be said that today the concept of “Information Security” began to be widely used not only on the side of scientists and specialists in the field of information technology, but also by representatives of all branches of state power, politicians, economists and financiers. Therefore, any state, any society is paying serious attention to the problem of Information Security. In other words, in the current world, the problems of ensuring information security - the protected state of the interests of a person, society and the state in the information industry-are of urgent importance. Because information is becoming a powerful force and becoming more dangerous than nuclear landfills. In the world, cases of nonlinear information dissemination, its negative interpretation or transmission in accordance with their own interests are in full swing. Therefore, ensuring information security is more important than ever. Therefore, it is necessary and necessary to study and implement methods of ensuring information security. Prevention of information attacks, ensuring information security - means protecting the country from internal and external risks .

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